

MATERIALS SCIENCE AND MECHANICS OF MACHINES

DETERMINATION OF THE IMPACT OF THE TECHNOLOGICAL PROCESS ON THE PERFORMANCE OF SAFETY DEVICES USED IN PRESSURE FACILITIES

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Abstract

The publication describes the influence of the technological process on certain parameters of safety devices used in pressure equipment. The defining technological parameters are shown and their influence on the reliability of manufactured safety devices used in pressure equipment is investigated.

Keywords: reliability in the production of safety devices for pressure equipment; safety devices; pressure equipment; pressure vessels; reliability of protective devices.

1. Introduction

The modern level of technological development provides great opportunities for achieving high levels of reliability of machines, mechanisms and devices. This, however, is associated with the incurrance of certain costs, which in certain cases may prove ineffective for the results that would be achieved. As a result, the cost-effectiveness of implementing a certain type of reliability improvement measures in the production of safety devices in pressure equipment should be assessed.

There are various options for increasing the reliability of safety devices. These possibilities can be related to improving the design, optimizing the production and technological processes in their manufacture and carrying out certain optimization measures during their operation. The application of these various options is acceptable only if the economic cumulative economic effect is evaluated and it is established that its value is positive and the final result will be achieved by guaranteeing a high degree of reliability with a proven low value of the applied optimization actions.

2. Impact Assessment Indicators (P_i)

2.1 Indicators in the manufacture of safety devices (P_m)

The indicators that are applicable for a sufficiently correct assessment at the production stage are design (p_d), manufacturing (p_p), testing (p_c), transport to the final destination (p_t), as well as other costs related to the realization of the final product (p_o). The value of the P_m indicator will be equal to the sum of all the constituent indicators, i.e.

$$P_m = p_d + p_p + p_c + p_t + p_o$$

$$P_i = P_m + P_u$$

If we assume that the influence of each of the constituent indicators can vary in the range from 0 to 1, it will mean that the maximum value of P_m can be 5, which will determine a range of changes in this parameter from 0 to 5, i.e.

$$0 \leq P_m \leq 5$$

2.2 Indicators influencing during the operation of safety devices (P_u)

The performance indicators that have a significant impact on the costs during the normal operation of safety devices in pressure equipment are related to all activities to ensure their normal operation and restore their operability when it has been disrupted.

These indicators are:

- Maintenance (m_t),
- Repair (m_r) and
- Prevention (m_p).

The value of the P_u indicator will be equal to the sum of all composite indicators, i.e.

$$P_u = m_t + m_r + m_p$$

If we assume that the influence of each of the constituent indicators can vary in the range from 0 to 1, it will mean that the maximum value of P_u can be 3, which will determine a range of changes in this parameter from 0 to 3, i.e.

$$0 \leq P_u \leq 3$$

As a result of what has been said so far, it can be concluded that the indicator for assessing the impact P_i is the sum of P_m and P_u

$$P_i = P_m + P_u$$

3. Influence of technological process parameters on operational parameters of safety devices

There is a connection between the operational and technological parameters, which is a function of various influences. Such influences can be the properties of the material from which the safety devices are made, the achieved accuracy of the final parameters of the device as a result of the process of its manufacture, the sufficient degree of reliability of the elements included in the device (springs, nozzles, etc.). This relationship can be described by the functional dependence, which is a function of a random argument

$$Q = f(X)$$

where,

X is a parameter of the safety device formed by the technological process

Q is the operational parameter of the safety device

The parameter Q may be, for example, the wear resistance determined by the rate of wear of the safety device, and may also include composite parameters for the wear resistance of the individual elements constituting the safety device.

Figure 1 shows the functional relationship between the parameter of the the safety device formed by the technological process " X " and the operational parameter of the safety device " Q ".

Figure 1

From the process shown in Figure 1, it is found that if sustainable control over the influence of the technological process is carried out and the production of a safety device with parameters lower than x_{min} is not allowed, it can be expected that the manufactured device will have a sufficient degree of reliability. Since the parameters Q and X are located in a complex stochastic relationship, this result cannot be achieved very easily. In addition, X is dependent not only on one, but also on more technological parameters. This means that their change will have a direct impact on the change in X . As a result of these influences, it can be expected that there is an increasing likelihood that the safety device of the pressure facility will produce an unacceptable Q value. In practice, this probability turns out to be of a high degree of real occurrence, since most often a smaller number of parameters of the manufactured safety device are subjected to control than the number of factors that affect its performance, which has a direct impact on its reliability.

4. Influence of the technological process on the reliability of safety devices in pressure equipment

The technological process of manufacturing a safety device is a complex and responsible complex cycle of activities. In its essence, it is a complex dynamic system that includes materials, production equipment, measuring instruments, control instruments, transport systems in the production process, working tools, production environment, personnel engaged in production and management of the entire process. Obviously, if any of these components is not sufficiently reliable, this will also

affect the reliability of the safety device being manufactured.

The technological process has many characteristics that create difficulties in ensuring its reliability, while at the same time this process has sufficient capabilities that, if used and combined, could have a significant and beneficial impact on ensuring the necessary degree of reliability of the manufactured safety device for pressure equipment. These difficulties arise as a result of the great complexity of the process itself, as well as as a result of the numerous stochastic relationships.

Along with this, the technological process also has a lot of opportunities to ensure sufficient reliability of the manufactured safety device. These possibilities are: changing the structure, by introducing additional controls and defining the operations of smaller ones, ensuring stable transitions between them, and designing technological systems in such a way that they become more adaptable and provide them with the possibility of changing their properties automatically or through self-regulation, by adapting to the specifics of the production process.

The main feature of the technological process is the interaction between its qualitative and quantitative indicators, i.e. a sufficient degree of reliability is guaranteed in achieving the corresponding high productivity. These indicators are in constant dynamic variability, and very often they enter into a contradiction mode.

The technological process considered as a system from the point of view of reliability must function stably in terms of both reliability and performance.

The reliability of the technological process is its property to ensure the production of the safety devices of the pressure equipment in the quantity for which it is designed while guaranteeing and ensuring the requirements for quality and safety of the manufactured product. It is a mistake to confuse the reliability of the technological process with its accuracy and stability. The accuracy of this process is its ability to ensure the correspondence between the scattering field of the value of the quality indicator of the manufactured safety device and the tolerance field set in accordance with the requirements and its location. Process stability is its ability to keep the quality indicators of the manufactured safety device within specified limits for a certain period of time.

The reliability of a technological process characterizes the dynamics of change in its indicators, and accuracy is the statics of this behavior for a given moment. As a result, accuracy should be considered as an integral part of process reliability. On the other hand, stability characterizes the process only in terms of maintaining quality indicators and does not affect the change in productivity. It is important to note that a technological process can be defined as stable, even if it produces safety devices with deviations from the requirements, i.e. the process can be stable, not without guaranteeing the necessary reliability. The reliability of the technological process should be evaluated only by

those parameters that depend on the manufacturing technology of safety devices. This means that the technological process can be reliable, but the manufactured safety device must have a relatively low degree of reliability.

The aspiration in creating the optimal conditions for achieving a successful final product of production should be, through the creation of a reliable production process, to achieve the guarantee of the established criteria for reliability of the finished product, which in this case is a safety device for pressure equipment.

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